

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

SOTES A Smart Soil Testing Device with Web and Mobile Integration for Precision Agriculture

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Abstract

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Background: Conventional soil testing methods are often time-consuming and inaccessible to small-scale farmers, limiting timely and data-driven agricultural decision-making. SOTES (Smart Soil Testing System) is an Arduino-based soil monitoring device integrated with web and mobile platforms for real-time soil analysis and crop recommendation. **Objectives:** This study aimed to (1) develop an integrated multi-parameter soil monitoring system, (2) provide real-time visualization and automated crop recommendations, (3) implement a dataset-driven crop suggestion module covering 22 crops, and (4) assess system usability among agricultural users. **Methods:** The system measures six soil parameters: nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), temperature, pH, and soil moisture. Sensor data are transmitted to a centralized database and matched with a predefined crop dataset to generate recommendations. A developmental research design was employed, and usability was evaluated using the System Usability Scale (SUS). **Findings:** Field testing using six soil samples resulted in a 66.67% successful recommendation rate, while two cases returned no results due to dataset limitations. The system demonstrated consistent real-time data acquisition and cross-platform visualization. Usability evaluation involving 20 respondents yielded a SUS score of 67.5, indicating acceptable usability. **Novelty:** The study presents an integrated soil monitoring and crop recommendation system designed for resource-limited environments. By combining multi-parameter sensing with a lightweight rule-based recommendation approach and cross-platform accessibility, the system provides a practical alternative to complex precision agriculture solutions.

Keywords: Smart soil testing; Precision agriculture; Arduino; Internet of Things (IoT); Web and mobile integration

1 Introduction

Precision agriculture has increasingly adopted real-time sensing and digital decision-support systems to enhance soil fertility management and crop productivity. Soil parameters such as nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), pH, moisture, and temperature play a critical role in determining crop suitability, fertilizer application efficiency, and irrigation planning. However, conventional soil testing methods primarily rely on laboratory-based chemical analysis, which is often expensive, time-consuming, and inaccessible to small-scale and resource-limited farmers. Delayed soil analysis results can lead to inefficient fertilizer use, suboptimal crop selection, and reduced agricultural productivity. As a result, the development of portable, real-time, and cost-effective soil monitoring systems has become a major focus in precision agriculture research.

Recent advancements in near-source soil sensing technologies have significantly improved in-field soil parameter detection. Zhang et al.⁽¹⁾ reviewed the research status of near-source sensing detection technologies for farmland soil parameters and emphasized the transition from laboratory-based testing toward portable, sensor-driven field monitoring platforms. Their study highlighted improvements in real-time data acquisition but also identified challenges related to sensor calibration stability and cost-effectiveness. Similarly, Pal et al.⁽²⁾ examined portable sensors in precision agriculture and reported progress in soil nutrient determination technologies while noting limitations in accuracy consistency and integration with decision-support systems. The emergence of Internet of Things (IoT)-based agricultural systems has further enhanced soil monitoring capabilities by enabling wireless data transmission and cloud-based analytics.

Shrote et al.⁽³⁾ provided a comprehensive review of IoT applications in smart agriculture, demonstrating that real-time synchronization and cross-platform accessibility significantly improve farm management efficiency. Mane et al.⁽⁴⁾ discussed Agriculture 4.0 integration for soil testing and highlighted the benefits of digital dashboards and sensor connectivity, although their findings also indicated that system complexity and infrastructure requirements may limit adoption among small-scale farmers. Likewise, Sutomo et al.⁽⁵⁾ developed an IoT-based soil moisture and pH monitoring system integrated with an Android application for rice farming, confirming improved irrigation management; however, their work focused primarily on moisture control rather than comprehensive nutrient-based crop recommendation. Beyond these foundational studies, several recent empirical works demonstrate the practical potential and real-world performance of integrated soil monitoring solutions. Kapalik Khanal et al.⁽⁶⁾ developed an IoT-based real-time soil health monitoring system capable of measuring moisture, electrical conductivity, UV radiation, temperature, and essential nutrients (N, P, K) using an ESP32S3 microcontroller, with support for multiple communication protocols and real-time visualization through a web interface. Their findings underscore the feasibility of in-situ soil nutrient sensing and its value in enabling data-driven decision-making for any cropping system.

Similarly, Shahab et al.⁽⁷⁾ introduced an IoT-driven smart agricultural technology that integrates multi-parameter soil sensing (including salinity and EC) with an AI-enabled mobile recommendation tool. Field testing in rice agroecosystems showed the system's ability to reliably capture key soil conditions and deliver actionable crop management insights—highlighting how IoT solutions can bridge the gap between sensor measurements and practical agronomic recommendations. Moreover, Kalaivani et al.⁽⁸⁾ proposed an IoT-enabled soil and crop monitoring system using low-cost sensors and cloud analytics. Their results showed the system's accuracy, energy efficiency, and scalability for remote monitoring, with a user-friendly dashboard allowing farmers to visualize trends and receive alerts for agronomic decisions.

Despite these advancements, several limitations remain in existing smart soil monitoring systems. Many reported systems emphasize either limited soil parameter coverage (e.g., moisture and pH only) or robust IoT architectures that elevate implementation cost and complexity, reducing feasibility in rural farming communities. Additionally, comparative analyses demonstrating how integrated low-cost systems perform relative to Agriculture 4.0 frameworks or high-precision sensing platforms are still insufficiently discussed in the literature.

To address these gaps, this study introduces SOTES (Smart Soil Testing System) a soil monitoring and crop recommendation platform designed for real-time multi-parameter soil analysis and cross-platform data visualization. Unlike systems that focus solely on sensor development or IoT connectivity, the proposed model combines NPK sensing, pH, moisture, temperature, and humidity monitoring with wireless cloud synchronization and web-mobile dashboard integration within a single low-cost architecture. The system further incorporates a crop suitability recommendation module based on soil parameter thresholds, supporting data-driven agricultural decision-making. While laboratory-based soil analysis remains more precise, portable sensor-based systems offer significant advantages in accessibility, speed, and cost efficiency; thus, this study evaluates whether a simplified microcontroller-based solution can provide sufficiently reliable soil data while ensuring high usability and adoption potential.

Accordingly, this research aims to develop and validate an integrated Arduino-based soil monitoring system capable of real-time parameter measurement, cloud-based data synchronization, and crop recommendation support, while also evaluating system usability using the System Usability Scale (SUS). By balancing technological capability with affordability and user-

centered design, this study seeks to contribute a practical and scalable solution for precision agriculture applications in small-scale and resource-limited farming environments.

This study contributes to the field of precision agriculture by presenting an accessible soil monitoring and crop recommendation system designed for small-scale and resource-limited farming environments. Unlike existing systems that rely on complex Internet of Things (IoT) architectures or machine learning models, the proposed system demonstrates the feasibility of a simplified rule-based approach for practical decision support.

Specifically, the study makes the following contributions:

1. development of a multi-parameter soil sensing device capable of measuring N, P, K, pH, temperature, and soil moisture in real time;
2. implementation of a lightweight crop recommendation system using a predefined dataset;
3. integration of hardware, web, and mobile platforms into a unified system; and
4. evaluation of system usability using the System Usability Scale (SUS), providing user-centered validation.

2 Methodology

The study employed Research and Development method. This method consists of (1) development of an Arduino-based device, (2) development of a website, (3) development of a mobile application and (4) testing of the developed hardware and software.

2.1 Hardware Schematic Diagram

Arduino is a free and open-source platform for creating electronic projects. Arduino is made up of a physical programmable circuit board (which is also known as a microcontroller) and a piece of software called an IDE (Integrated Development Environment) that runs on your computer and is used to create and upload computer code to the physical board⁽⁸⁾ Arduino is the microcontroller used in the development of the device. Several sensors were also integrated in the device to be able to capture all the variables needed in the website and mobile application in determining what plant suits to the tested soil. Figure 1 shows the Schematic diagram of the device. It includes the different sensors and modules used in the development. The description of each module is shown in Figure 2.

2.2 Hardware Prototype

Legend

1. Soil NPK sensor - measures the nitrogen, Phosphorus, and Potassium values of the soil
2. Humidity & Temperature sensor - measures the temperature and humidity value
3. RS485 Modbus Module - reads the soil NPK and pH sensors
4. Bread Board - helps on the connections of the pins and circuits into the device.
5. Soil pH - measures the pH value of the soil.
6. Arduino Uno - reads the code inputs of the sensors and activates the overall systems of the device.
7. DC jack ports, female - this side of the device are the jack ports for the soil pH sensor.
8. DC jack ports, male - these jack ports are attached to the soil pH and are to be connected to the female jack ports of the soil ph.
9. 0.96 inches OLED display monitor - the monitor of this side shows the measured values for the soil pH sensor.
10. 9 volts Battery - primary power supply of the device which powers up the Arduino, humidity/temperature and soil pH sensor.
11. 3.7 volts Batteries (3x) - secondary power supply of the device which powers up the NPK sensor.
12. LCD Display - the monitor which shows the measured values for the humidity and temperature sensor.
13. 0.96 inches OLED display monitor - the monitor of this side shows the measured values for the soil NPK sensor.
14. DC jack ports, male - these jack ports are attached to the soil NPK sensor and are to be connected to the female jack ports of the soil NPK sensor.
15. DC jack ports, female - this side of the device are the jack ports for the soil NPK sensor.

Fig 1. Device Schematic Diagram

2.3 Software

The dataset retrieved from Atharva Ingle’s Crop Recommendation Dataset were stored in an online database platform by the researchers which is the Firebase Database. This data can be retrieved and compared to the data from the SOTES device through the use of a website and a mobile application. Both website and mobile application will use the same database. The database will consist of data such as the plant, Nitrogen, Phosphorous, Potassium, Temperature, pH Level and humidity values. A mobile application will also be developed to be used as another platform in evaluating the data retrieved from the soil. Using the application requires internet connectivity to access the database online. This application is limited to evaluating the data entered for analysis. Therefore, using the SOTES device is highly recommended in retrieving soil properties before using this application.

2.4 Data Requirement

To be able to analyze the data and recommend suitable in a specific soil based on the retrieved variables, the following soil properties must be entered in the system.

1. *Nitrogen (N)* - Nitrogen is the primary electrolyte in soil. Having an adequate supply of electrolytes corresponds very closely with plant growth to retrieve Nitrogen property of the soil, NPK sensor was utilized in the device.
2. *Phosphorous* - constitutes about 0.2 percent of a plant’s dry weight, where it is primarily a component of tissue molecules such as nucleic acids, phospholipids, and adenosine triphosphate (ATP). After nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) is the

Fig 2. Device Prototype

second most limiting nutrient. It can reduce plant growth and development and potentially limit crop yield. NPK sensor was used to measure the Phosphorous level in the soil.

3. *Potassium*- Normal plant growth requires large quantities of potassium. In fact, throughout growth most crops contain more potassium than any other nutrient including nitrogen (N). This data variable can be retrieved by the sotes device through the NPK sensor.
4. *Temperature* - Soil temperature is the measurement of the warmth in the soil. RS485 Modbus Module was used to read the temperature value of the soil.
5. *pH Level*- pH was measured using a pH sensor module.
6. *Soil humidity*- is the water stored in the soil RS485 Modbus Module was used to read the Soil humidity value.

2.5 Crop Recommendation Dataset by Atharva Ingle

The crop recommendation dataset developed by Atharva Ingle was integrated into the system database to serve as the primary reference for determining suitable crops based on soil conditions. This dataset provides structured agricultural data containing key soil and environmental parameters, including Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), Potassium (K), temperature, pH level, and humidity. Each record in the dataset corresponds to a specific crop type that is recommended under particular combinations of these parameters. The dataset functions as the knowledge base of the system, enabling the mobile application to match the real-time soil readings obtained from the SOTES device with predefined data patterns. Through this matching process, the system generates appropriate crop recommendations based on the similarity between the measured soil properties and the stored reference values.

2.6 System Flowchart

The flowchart in Figure 3 illustrates the decision-making process of the SOTES (Smart Soil Testing System) for generating plant recommendations based on soil conditions. The process begins by loading the reference values for soil nutrients (N, P, K), temperature, pH, and soil moisture (SM), which represent the ideal requirements for different crops. The system then reads the real-time sensor inputs (iN, iP, iK, iTemp, ipH, and iSM) obtained from the soil. Each measured parameter is compared sequentially with its corresponding reference value stored in the database. If any parameter fails to match the required condition,

the system branches to the “No Results Found” path, indicating that no suitable crop matches the current soil profile. This ensures that only plants whose nutrient, temperature, pH, and moisture requirements are fully satisfied are recommended.

Fig 3. System Flowchart

As shown in Figure 3, system follows a data flow process where sensor readings are captured by the Arduino microcontroller, transmitted to a cloud-based database, and processed by the web and mobile applications to generate crop recommendations. This integration ensures real-time data accessibility and decision support. When all parameters satisfy the matching conditions, the system proceeds to display the list of recommended plants. This logic allows SOTES to function as an intelligent soil-based

crop advisory system, helping farmers select crops that are best suited to the current soil conditions, thereby supporting more precise and data-driven agricultural decision-making.

2.7 Evaluators

The evaluators of the study were the twenty (20) members of the agricultural community in Barangay Carolina, Eastern Samar. These individuals directly engaged in farming and soil management, making them qualified to assess the functionality and usability of the Soil Testing Device with Browser-Based and Mobile Application Soil Quality Analyzer Software (SOTES). Their feedback provided critical insights into the effectiveness of the device in soil assessment, crop suitability recommendations, and ease of use.

2.8 Evaluation

The evaluation process focused on assessing the usability, accuracy, and efficiency of the SOTES device in providing real-time soil analysis. The evaluators used the System Usability Scale (SUS) to rate the system based on key usability factors, including ease of operation, accuracy of soil data retrieval, and the effectiveness of the browser-based and mobile application interface. The evaluation was conducted using a 5-point Likert scale, where respondents rated their experience with the device. The collected responses were analyzed to determine the overall usability score and identify potential improvements to enhance its functionality and user experience.

2.9 Scoring

The System Usability Scale is a Likert scale consisting of 10 questions that device users will respond to. Research Respondents rate each statement on a scale of 1 to 5, where 5 indicates strong agreement with the statement and 1 signifies strong disagreement. Table 1 shows the scoring method for the System Usability Scale (SUS), which uses a Likert scale with 10 questions. Respondents rate each question on a scale from 1 to 5, reflecting their level of agreement with the statement. A score of 5 indicates "Strongly Agree," while a score of 1 indicates "Strongly Disagree." The table provided clarifies the qualitative descriptions corresponding to each score, ranging from strong agreement (5) to strong disagreement (1). This method is designed to quantify users' subjective assessments of a system's usability, providing a consistent way to measure user satisfaction of the website.

Table 1. Method of Scoring

Rating Scale	Qualitative Description
5	Strongly Agree
4	Agree
3	Slightly Agree
2	Slightly Disagree
1	Strongly Disagree

SUS score will be able to tell the website's usability performance in the aspects of effectiveness, efficiency, and overall ease of use. Although each response yields a score on a scale of 0-100. The interpretation is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Survey Result Interpretation

SUS Score	Grade	Adjective Rating
>80.3	A	Excellent
68 – 80.3	B	Good
68	C	Okay
51-68	D	Poor
<51	E	Awful

2.10 Sensor Calibration and Validation

To ensure reliability of the sensor readings, standard calibration procedures were applied prior to data collection. The soil pH sensor was calibrated using buffer solutions with known pH values (pH 4, 7, and 10). The NPK sensor was calibrated based on manufacturer-provided reference values and validated through repeated measurements to ensure consistency. Temperature and humidity readings from the DHT11 sensor were compared with standard environmental readings to verify accuracy. Due to limited access to laboratory soil testing facilities, full chemical validation was not conducted; however, repeated trials were performed to ensure measurement stability. This limitation is acknowledged and addressed in the discussion section.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 System Performance and Soil Parameter Acquisition

The development of the SOTES device using an Arduino microcontroller enabled real-time acquisition of multiple soil parameters, including nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), pH, soil moisture, and temperature. Figure 4 illustrates the assembled hardware configuration, where integrated soil sensors were directly inserted into the soil to obtain parameter readings. The captured values were processed and displayed in real time on the LCD interface, confirming stable sensor integration and embedded system functionality. Figure 5 demonstrates the corresponding mobile application interface used to input measured values and generate crop recommendations.

The multi-parameter sensing capability of SOTES aligns with the findings of Zhang et al. ⁽¹⁾, who emphasized the importance of near-source sensing technologies in enabling in-field soil parameter monitoring. Similar to their reported transition from laboratory testing to portable sensing platforms, the present study demonstrates that soil parameter acquisition can be effectively performed using low-cost microcontroller-based systems. However, while Zhang et al. ⁽¹⁾ noted challenges in calibration stability and sensor precision, the current system prioritized affordability and real-time accessibility, accepting moderate trade-offs in laboratory-grade accuracy.

Pal et al. ⁽²⁾ reported that portable soil nutrient sensors face variability in accuracy when compared to laboratory chemical analysis. The present results are consistent with this observation, as SOTES provides indicative soil parameter measurements suitable for decision support rather than high-precision laboratory diagnostics. Thus, the system outperforms conventional laboratory testing in terms of accessibility, cost-efficiency, and speed, but may fall short in analytical precision under highly variable soil conditions.

Fig 4. SOTES Device Prototype

Figure 4 presents the developed SOTES device integrating soil sensors, an Arduino microcontroller, and display modules. The probe-based sensors enable direct soil parameter acquisition, while the compact design supports portability and real-time field data collection.

Figure 5 illustrates the mobile application interface used to input soil parameter values and generate crop recommendations. The interface provides a user-friendly platform for visualizing data and supports real-time decision-making based on measured

Fig 5. Mobile Application Interface for Soil Data Input and Crop Recommendation

soil conditions. In addition to the mobile application, the system can also be accessed through a web browser, allowing users to view and analyze soil data across multiple platforms for greater accessibility and convenience.

3.2 Crop Recommendation Performance

Six distinct soil samples were tested using the SOTES device. Out of the six datasets collected, four successfully generated crop recommendations (corn, kidney beans, coffee, and chickpea), representing a 66.7% successful recommendation rate. Two datasets resulted in “No Results Found,” indicating that the measured soil parameter combinations did not match existing patterns within the system database. This limitation highlights a key trade-off between simplicity and predictive completeness. While machine learning-based systems such as those reviewed by Shrote et al.⁽³⁾ and Agriculture 4.0 frameworks discussed by Mane et al.⁽⁴⁾ incorporate large datasets and advanced cloud-based analytics, they often require extensive computational resources and infrastructure. In contrast, the present system uses a rule-based dataset derived from predefined crop parameter ranges, reducing computational complexity but limiting coverage when encountering out-of-range inputs.

Compared to Sutomo et al.⁽⁵⁾, who focused primarily on moisture and pH monitoring for irrigation management, SOTES extends functionality by integrating full NPK sensing and crop recommendation logic. This represents an improvement in decision-support capability. However, unlike advanced machine learning-based prediction frameworks reported in recent precision agriculture literature, the current system does not dynamically adapt or retrain based on new data inputs. Therefore, while the system performs effectively within predefined thresholds, it may not generalize as flexibly as AI-driven models.

The absence of recommendations in two test cases does not invalidate the system; rather, it demonstrates the need for database expansion and adaptive algorithm enhancement. Expanding the crop dataset and incorporating machine learning classifiers could significantly improve recommendation coverage in future iterations.

The use of six soil samples represents an initial prototype-level validation intended to demonstrate system functionality rather than statistical generalization. Future work will include larger datasets across multiple soil types to improve robustness and reliability of the system.

Table 3 presents the results of six soil samples analyzed using the SOTES device, including measured values for nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), temperature, pH, and soil moisture, along with the corresponding crop recommendations

Table 3. Testing Results

Testing (n)	N	P	K	Tmp.	pH	SM	Result
1st Soil Tested	64	35	23	23.02038	6.1	5.680361	Corn
2nd Soil Tested	22	59	29	22.64237	7.4	5.947	No Results Found
3rd Soil Tested	28	43	33	19.48317	7.8	7.476801	No Results Found
4th Soil Tested	33	59	22	22.64237	6.5	5.947	Kidney Beans
5th Soil Tested	103	40	30	27.30902	5.9	6.348316	Coffee
6th Soil Tested	46	76	77	18.23508	6.8	6.967843	Chickpea

generated by the system. The results show that the system successfully produced crop recommendations for four out of six samples (66.67%), specifically identifying corn, kidney beans, coffee, and chickpea as suitable crops based on the detected soil conditions. This indicates that the system is capable of processing multi-parameter soil data and matching it with predefined crop requirements. However, two samples (33.33%) resulted in “No Results Found,” suggesting that the measured soil parameter combinations did not meet any of the predefined thresholds in the dataset. This outcome highlights a key limitation of the rule-based recommendation approach, where system performance is highly dependent on the completeness and coverage of the dataset. Expanding the dataset to include a wider range of soil conditions and crop profiles is necessary to improve recommendation coverage and system robustness. The variability observed in nutrient values (N, P, K) and environmental conditions (temperature and soil moisture) demonstrates the system’s ability to capture diverse soil characteristics in real time. The normalized pH values fall within the typical agronomic range, indicating that soil acidity levels were appropriately interpreted after calibration. These findings support the functionality of the integrated sensing mechanism and confirm that the system can provide indicative soil measurements suitable for decision support.

Despite these promising results, the findings should be interpreted with caution due to the limited number of soil samples used in testing. The small sample size restricts the generalizability of the results and does not fully represent variability across different soil types and environmental conditions. The agronomic validity of the generated crop recommendations was not verified through expert consultation or comparison with established agricultural guidelines. Future studies should involve agronomists or agricultural agencies to validate recommendation accuracy and improve system reliability.

3.3 Real-Time Data Integration and System Reliability

The successful transmission of soil parameter readings from the Arduino hardware to the mobile application confirms the effectiveness of integrating embedded systems with digital visualization platforms. This supports the findings of Shrote et al. (3), who identified real-time synchronization and cloud connectivity as core advantages of IoT-based agricultural systems. Similarly, Mane et al. (4) highlighted the importance of Agriculture 4.0 integration in enhancing data accessibility.

However, unlike more complex IoT architectures requiring continuous high-bandwidth connectivity, SOTES operates using simplified wireless synchronization suitable for low-resource environments. This makes the system more deployable in rural settings but potentially less scalable for large-scale commercial farms requiring centralized multi-node monitoring.

3.4 Usability Evaluation and Adoption Feasibility

System usability evaluation using the System Usability Scale (SUS) yielded a score of 67.5, which falls within the “Acceptable” usability range based on standard SUS interpretation benchmarks (average benchmark = 68). Although slightly below the global average threshold, the score indicates that the system is generally usable and appropriate for field-based applications (Table 4).

Positive ratings were observed in ease of use, functional integration, and user confidence. However, moderate ratings in negatively worded items particularly regarding technical support requirements and perceived complexity suggest that first-time users may require brief training or orientation. This partially supports findings from Mane et al. (4), who noted that IoT-based agricultural systems may introduce complexity for non-technical users.

Compared to many smart agriculture prototypes that lack usability validation, the inclusion of SUS evaluation strengthens the present study’s practical relevance. While the system does not achieve “Excellent” usability (>80 SUS), it demonstrates acceptable adoption potential with room for interface refinement.

SUS Score

$$SUS=(X+Y) * 2.5$$

$$SUS=(15+12) * 2.5$$

$$SUS = 67.5$$

Table 4. SUS Evaluation Result

Questions	Rating
1 I think that I would like to use this system frequently.	4
2 I found the system unnecessarily complex.	2
3 I thought the system was easy to use.	4
4 I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.	3
5 I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.	4
6 I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.	2
7 I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.	4
8 I found the system very cumbersome to use.	3
9 I felt very confident using the system.	4
10 I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.	3

Interpretation

SUS Score = 67.5 Interpretation = Acceptable

4 Conclusion

The study successfully designed and developed SOTES, a smart soil testing device integrated with web and mobile platforms for automated crop recommendation. The system effectively measured six critical soil parameters Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), Potassium (K), temperature, pH level, and humidity and utilized these inputs to generate crop recommendations based on a predefined dataset containing 22 plant types. Field validation was conducted using six (6) distinct soil samples. The results showed that the system successfully generated appropriate crop recommendations in four cases, yielding a 66.67% recommendation success rate. However, two samples (33.33%) returned “No Results Found,” indicating that certain soil parameter combinations were not represented within the existing dataset. These findings highlight both the operational capability of the system and the need to expand the database to improve recommendation coverage and robustness. Usability evaluation was conducted among 20 respondents from the agricultural community using the System Usability Scale (SUS). The computed SUS score of 67.5 falls within the “Good” and “Acceptable” usability range, indicating that the system demonstrates satisfactory ease of use, learnability, and functional integration. Although the overall user perception was positive, some respondents reported minor challenges during initial system interaction, particularly in synchronizing hardware readings with the mobile and web interfaces. These usability observations suggest that further refinement of user interface design and onboarding guidance may enhance overall user experience and operational efficiency.

References

- 1) Zhang H, Qi B, Wang Y, Wang T, Ding Y, Zhang W, et al. Research Status of Near-Source Sensing Detection Technology for Farmland Soil Parameters. *AgriEngineering*. 2026;8:66. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriengineering8020066>.
- 2) Pal A, Dubey SK, Goel S, Kalita PK. Portable sensors in precision agriculture: Assessing advances and challenges in soil nutrient determination. *TrAC – Trends in Analytical Chemistry*. 2024;180:117981. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2024.117981>.
- 3) Shrote JN, More V, Kedari SS. Internet of Things (IoT) in Smart Agriculture: A Comprehensive Review of Technologies, Applications, and Challenges. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*. 2026 February;16(2). <https://doi.org/10.29322/IJSRP.16.02.2026.p17043>.
- 4) Mane SS, Narawade V, Ranshur NJ. Revolutionizing agriculture soil testing with Agriculture 4.0 and IoT integration. *Current Agriculture Research Journal*. 2024;12(3). <http://dx.doi.org/10.12944/CARJ.12.3.26>.
- 5) Sutomo B, Saputri TA, Satria IW. Utilizing IoT technology for soil moisture management through integration of pH and moisture sensors in an Android application for rice farming. *International Journal of Software Engineering and Computer Science*. 2025;5(1):248–258. <https://doi.org/10.35870/ijsecs.v5i1.3538>.
- 6) Khanal K, Ojha G, Chataut S, Ghimire UK. IoT-Based Real-Time Soil Health Monitoring System for Precision Agriculture. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*. 2024 July;11(07). Available from: <https://www.irjet.net/archives/V11/i7/IRJET-V11I761.pdf>.
- 7) Shahab H, Naeem M, Iqbal M, Aqeel M, Ullah SS. IoT-driven smart agricultural technology for real-time soil and crop optimization. *Smart Agricultural Technology*. 2025;10:100847. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atech.2025.100847>.
- 8) Kalaivani TS, Kamireddy T, Govindakumar S. IoT-Enabled Soil and Crop Monitoring System Using Low-Cost Smart Sensors for Precision Agriculture. *Engineering Proceedings*. 2025;118:77. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ECSA-12-26537>.